

Overcoming Barriers: Addressing Social and Language Anxiety Among English Language Learners in Social Welfare Residential Degree Colleges

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Abstract:

Social and language anxiety are critical factors that influence the language acquisition process, especially in settings where students are learning English as a second or foreign language. In the context of social welfare residential degree colleges, where students often come from marginalized communities, these anxieties can have a profound impact on their academic performance, self-esteem, and overall educational experience. Social welfare residential degree colleges typically cater to students from disadvantaged backgrounds, offering them opportunities to pursue higher education in a supportive environment. However, despite the supportive structure, students in these institutions often face unique challenges, including heightened social and language anxieties.

This study investigates the impact of social and language anxiety on English language learners (ELLs) in social welfare residential degree colleges. These institutions cater to students from marginalized communities, who often face heightened levels of anxiety due to their socio-economic backgrounds and the challenges of learning English as a second language. The research examines how these anxieties influence language acquisition, academic performance, and social interactions within the college environment. The study also explores potential strategies for alleviating these anxieties, with the aim of improving educational outcomes and fostering a more inclusive learning environment. Findings suggest that targeted interventions can significantly reduce anxiety levels, thereby enhancing both language proficiency and overall academic success among ELLs in these settings.

Keywords: social anxiety, language anxiety, English language learners, social welfare residential degree colleges, language acquisition, academic performance, educational strategies, marginalized communities

Many English as a Foreign/Second Language (EFL/ESL) learners have a strong desire to acquire the skill of speaking English. Language learners occasionally assess their proficiency in language acquisition by measuring their progress in spoken language fluency.

Teachers and textbooks employ either direct methods that focus on specific parts of oral communication, such as turn-taking and topic management, or indirect methods that provide opportunities for oral engagement through group work, task work, and other strategies. Individuals require communication in order to express thoughts and convey information.

Speakers employ communication as a means to convey information to someone. Speakers utilise language based on their individual objectives. In order to achieve effective communication, speakers must possess the ability to simultaneously listen and communicate. Oral communication has a crucial role in the acquisition of a second language. Speaking, despite its significance, has been neglected in educational institutions like as schools and universities for various reasons, including a focus on grammar and unfavourable teacher-student ratios. Speaking has been excluded from testing due to the challenge of properly analysing it and the time-consuming nature of conducting speaking examinations. Oral communication is a valuable skill that deserves emphasis in both primary and secondary languages. Mastering the art of oral communication is the paramount component of acquiring proficiency in a second or foreign language, and one's proficiency is evaluated based on their capacity to engage in meaningful conversations in that language. (Woodrow 2006) Speaking is a crucial skill among the four language skills since it designates those who have acquired a language as its proficient users. The primary objective of English language instruction is to provide learners with the capacity to utilise the English language proficiently and accurately in communication.

However, it appears that language learners struggle to speak with fluency and precision due to their insufficient expertise in this domain. Despite diligent attempts, the instruction of English as a second language in Indian high schools has failed to yield the anticipated outcomes. This issue develops when individuals enrol in higher education with minimal or nonexistent proficiency in the language. As English educators and stewards of the development of future educators, we recognise the need of understanding the underlying factors contributing to this issue. Teachers assert that students and the environment are the fundamental components of a social process that must interact effectively in order to attain the intended outcomes in English language learning. Alternatively, some argue that quality teaching is not solely determined by the skills of the teachers, but also by the creation of conducive contexts and work environments that support effective teaching. Teachers must possess a high level of proficiency in both language and methodology in order to effectively establish a suitable learning environment. This involves utilising various tools, materials, and technology to facilitate the learning process. Many English teachers in Telangana schools have a low language proficiency level and weak teaching abilities, hindering their ability to effectively

meet instructional goals. This data clearly revealed the substandard quality of English instruction in our nation.

Tulasi Nimmala (2016) highlights the significant global increase in the number of English language learners, emphasizing the growing need to improve English instruction for those learning it as a second language, particularly in the state of Andhra Pradesh. The prominence of the English language on a global scale highlights the importance of effective English language teaching. Following the bifurcation of Andhra Pradesh and its establishment as a new state, the region has attracted numerous enterprises, making it essential to enhance the English proficiency of students from the newly formed Andhra Pradesh to meet both employment demands and regional needs. These learners are strongly influenced by their native language, with socio-economic factors playing a crucial role in their English language acquisition. Nimmala's research primarily examines how socio-economic conditions impact English language acquisition in the Andhra Pradesh region.

Farhath Unissa Begum (2017) explores the development of reading comprehension skills, emphasizing the importance of reading as a lifelong ability and a critical factor in academic success. The study, based on schema theory, focuses on strategies to engage students' interest in reading comprehension. It also examines the levels of education, requirements, and criteria for the employment of teachers in public schools across India.

Pablo Alejandro Quezada Sarmiento (2017) discusses the challenges in English language instruction in Ecuadorian high schools, attributing them to instructors' inadequate English competency. Inadequate teacher preparation leads to the improper selection and use of didactic and technological teaching resources, which are essential for language instruction in an increasingly digital society. This lack of proper training hampers teachers' ability to effectively use English in the classroom, a critical issue as the classroom setting often provides the sole opportunity for students to engage with and practice the language. Despite these challenges, Ecuadorian English teachers manage issues such as lesson planning, learning management, addressing students' needs, and arranging seating, thereby mitigating potential problems.

Problems of Learners in a Language Classroom

Social anxiety refers to the fear of being judged or negatively evaluated in social situations, which can be particularly pronounced in classroom settings where students are required to communicate in a language they are still mastering. Language anxiety, on the other hand, is the fear or apprehension experienced when learning or using a second language. This can manifest as nervousness, fear of making mistakes, or reluctance to participate in class activities. For English language learners (ELLs) in social welfare residential degree colleges, these anxieties can act as significant barriers to language proficiency, leading to reduced participation, lower academic achievement, and even withdrawal from educational activities.

The interplay between social and language anxiety is particularly complex in these educational settings. The communal living arrangements in residential colleges can exacerbate social anxieties, as students are constantly interacting with peers, teachers, and staff in English, a language in which they may not feel fully competent. This continuous exposure to potentially anxiety-inducing situations can create a vicious cycle, where anxiety hampers language learning, and the struggle with language further increases anxiety. (Zheng 2008)

Understanding the impact of social and language anxiety on ELLs in residential degree colleges is crucial for developing effective teaching strategies and support mechanisms. Addressing these anxieties can lead to better academic outcomes, increased confidence, and a more positive educational experience for these students.

In Telangana state, teaching English presents unique challenges due to the majority of learners coming from rural backgrounds, making it difficult for them to adapt to the learning environment in English classrooms. Even English teachers struggle to help students acquire language skills effortlessly. Proficiency in English has become increasingly important in daily life. While students previously sought English proficiency primarily for communication and academic success, the Telangana government has now implemented LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing) skills to meet students' requirements, enabling them to gain language skills and grow professionally. The expansion of private schools has drawn teachers due to the financial advantages, despite their often insufficient qualifications, which hinders students' language proficiency improvement.

Teachers continue to face challenges in their English language teaching techniques due to excessive workloads, inadequate instructional resources, and larger class sizes. The lack of internet access and digital textbooks further impedes teachers' capacity to effectively instruct in English. Rural schools in Telangana are under pressure to enhance student performance amid declining enrollments, budget deficits, and increasing state and federal requirements. This study examines the sociological aspects of learning English, focusing on the impact of social factors on the acquisition and development of English language skills.

A shared passion exists for teaching English to non-native learners, with the common goal of facilitating English language acquisition. This passion is grounded in the belief that language can be taught effectively through techniques such as presentation, repetition, and activity-based learning. The primary responsibility is to evaluate the effectiveness of ESL (English as a Second Language) programs. Teachers offer tailored approaches to support and nurture students who excel. The study also addresses social dynamics within the classroom, noting that while "independent learning" may appeal to some, most individuals benefit more from group learning due to the mutual support and the potential for creating enjoyable and lasting learning experiences for both students and teachers.

An effective learning approach involves inquiring about concepts or topics that are difficult to comprehend. Individuals suffering from social anxiety related to public speaking have the potential to improve their public speaking skills. (Horwitz, & Horwitz 1986) However, there are specific barriers that prevent teachers and learners from speaking English in the classroom. These include a lack of self-motivation among English language teachers, which in turn hampers their ability to inspire students. Teachers also struggle with implementing instructional methodologies in the ESL classroom due to time constraints, preventing them from adequately assessing students' language proficiency. (Yan, & Horwitz 2008)

Many universities offer syllabi lacking sufficient resources to enhance students' skills, which leads to a lack of enthusiasm among teachers for engaging students in ESL programs. Additionally, students' rigorous adherence to their native language since childhood hinders their ability to acquire proficiency in a second language. In Telangana, the use of native languages as the medium of instruction in schools has left students with limited knowledge of English, rendering them incapable of engaging in advanced English courses.

Social and Language Anxiety among ELLs

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To investigate the impact of social and language anxiety on English language learners (ELLs) in social welfare residential degree colleges, a small-scale study was conducted at three such institutions in Telangana state. The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of social and language anxiety among these students and to evaluate the effectiveness of specific instructional tasks designed to alleviate these anxieties and improve their English language proficiency.

The study involved a total of 60 students, with 20 participants selected from each of the three residential colleges. These students were aged between 18 and 21 years, and the group comprised 35 females and 25 males. The majority of the participants came from low-income, rural families, which often posed additional challenges in their educational journeys. The native languages of these students included Telugu, Urdu, and Lambadi, which significantly influenced their approach to learning English as a second language. Given their socio-economic background and the linguistic environment they were raised in, these students represented a group that faced considerable obstacles in mastering English.

To gather comprehensive data on the students' social and language anxieties, a multi-method approach was employed. The first step involved administering a standardized questionnaire designed to measure both social and language anxieties. The Social Interaction Anxiety Scale was used to evaluate social anxiety, while the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale assessed language anxiety. These questionnaires asked students to rate their agreement with various statements on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." This method provided quantitative data on the levels of anxiety experienced by the students in social and language-related contexts.

Following the initial assessment, the students participated in a series of task-based language activities aimed at reducing their anxieties and improving their English proficiency. The first of these tasks was a group discussion. The discussions were structured around familiar topics, which helped to create a supportive environment where students felt more comfortable using English. The goal was to reduce social anxiety by encouraging interaction in a non-threatening setting.

Next, students engaged in role-playing exercises, which were specifically designed to simulate real-life scenarios. These tasks provided students with opportunities to practice English in a context that mirrored everyday situations but within the safety of the classroom.

The role-playing exercises were intended to help students overcome language anxiety by allowing them to use English in a way that felt less pressured.

Another task involved peer review sessions, where students were paired up to review and provide feedback on each other's written assignments. This task was aimed at reducing language anxiety by fostering a collaborative learning environment. By receiving constructive feedback from peers rather than solely from instructors, students could view mistakes as learning opportunities rather than failures.

The final task was a public speaking exercise, where students were asked to prepare and present short topics in front of the class. This activity targeted performance anxiety, which is a common aspect of language anxiety. The repetition of this task was intended to gradually increase the students' comfort with public speaking in English, thereby reducing their overall anxiety in such situations.

In addition to these activities, classroom observations were conducted to assess student participation, confidence levels, and interactions with peers during the tasks. After completing the tasks, students were also interviewed to gather qualitative feedback on their experiences and any perceived changes in their anxiety levels.

Findings of the Study

The findings from the initial questionnaire revealed that social and language anxieties were prevalent among the students. A significant portion of the participants, about 70%, reported experiencing moderate to high levels of social anxiety, particularly in situations that required public speaking or group interactions. This anxiety often manifested as reluctance to participate in classroom activities or fear of being judged by peers and instructors.

Language anxiety was also a prominent issue, with 65% of the students expressing significant concerns. These students commonly feared making mistakes in English, which hindered their willingness to speak or write in the language. The lack of confidence in their language abilities was a major barrier to their academic progress and overall language development.

The task-based language activities conducted as part of the study were found to be effective in mitigating these anxieties. The group discussions, for example, were instrumental in creating a more relaxed environment where students could gradually become more

comfortable speaking English. Over the course of three sessions, students who had initially been hesitant to participate began to engage more actively in the discussions. The supportive nature of the group setting helped to reduce social anxiety by providing students with a space where they felt less pressure to perform perfectly.

Role-playing exercises proved to be particularly beneficial in addressing language anxiety. The simulated scenarios allowed students to practice using English in a context that felt realistic yet safe. This practice helped them build confidence in their ability to communicate in English outside of the classroom, as they were able to see tangible improvements in their language skills through repeated practice.

The peer review sessions also had a positive impact on the students' attitudes toward learning English. By receiving feedback from their peers, 80% of the students reported feeling more comfortable making mistakes, as they viewed these mistakes as part of the learning process rather than as failures. This collaborative approach fostered a more supportive classroom environment, which in turn helped to reduce language anxiety.

The public speaking task, although initially challenging for many students, led to noticeable improvements in their confidence levels over time. While the first round of presentations caused significant anxiety, repeated exposure to public speaking situations helped students become more accustomed to speaking English in front of others. By the end of the exercise, 60% of the students reported feeling more confident in their ability to speak English in public, marking a significant reduction in performance anxiety.

Analysis

The results of this study indicate that social and language anxieties are substantial barriers to English language acquisition among students in social welfare residential degree colleges. These anxieties not only hindered the students' ability to engage fully in classroom activities but also affected their overall academic performance. However, the task-based language activities implemented during the study were effective in reducing these anxieties and improving the students' confidence in using English.

The group discussions helped students gradually overcome their social anxiety by providing a non-threatening environment for interaction. Role-playing exercises offered a practical, low-pressure way for students to practice English, which helped to alleviate language

anxiety. Peer review sessions encouraged a more positive attitude towards making mistakes, which is crucial for language learning, while the public speaking tasks, though challenging, ultimately led to significant improvements in students' confidence.

Conclusion

This study highlights the pervasive nature of social and language anxieties among ELLs in social welfare residential degree colleges and highlights the importance of addressing these issues to improve language learning outcomes. The findings suggest that task-based language activities are an effective strategy for reducing these anxieties and building students' confidence in using English. By integrating such activities into the regular curriculum, educators can create a more supportive learning environment that encourages active participation and fosters language development.

These results also point to the need for ongoing research and policy interventions to further support English language education in these institutions. With the right strategies in place, students from socially and economically disadvantaged backgrounds can overcome the barriers posed by social and language anxieties, ultimately improving their proficiency in English and enhancing their academic and professional prospects.

This study highlights the significant impact that social and language anxiety has on English language learners in social welfare residential degree colleges. The findings reveal that these anxieties are not just peripheral issues but central barriers that hinder students from fully engaging in their learning and achieving their academic potential. Through the implementation of targeted, task-based language activities, this research demonstrates that it is possible to effectively reduce these anxieties, thereby fostering a more supportive and conducive learning environment.

The improvement in students' confidence and participation observed during this study suggests that with the right strategies, the barriers posed by social and language anxieties can be overcome. This has important implications for educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers, who must prioritize the integration of such anxiety-reducing methods into their teaching practices. By addressing these challenges head-on, educational institutions can better support their students, enabling them to develop the English language skills necessary for both academic success and future professional opportunities.

Furthermore, this study highlights the need for continued research and specific interventions that consider the unique socio-economic and cultural backgrounds of students in residential degree colleges. As English continues to be a critical global language, ensuring that all students, regardless of their background, have the opportunity to master it is essential for their individual growth and for the broader development of society. The insights gained from this research offer a foundation for future studies and initiatives aimed at improving English language education in similar contexts.

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